

Kinetics and Catalysis of Thermal Decomposition of Potassium Chlorate and Potassium Bromate— A Thermogravimetric Study

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A comparative study of the kinetics and mechanism of thermal decomposition of potassium chlorate and potassium bromate catalysed by CuO and MnO₂ has been made by dynamic thermogravimetry. The kinetic parameters for the processes, based on Coats-Redfern equation and mechanistic equations, have been determined. The MnO₂ catalysed decomposition of KClO₃ proceeds by Mampel mechanism, while that of KBrO₃ satisfies the Avrami mechanism.

THE technical importance of thermal decomposition of oxyhalogen salts has attracted considerable attention in recent years¹⁻⁶. In the present paper, kinetics of uncatalysed, and metal oxide-catalysed thermal decomposition of potassium chlorate and potassium bromate have been discussed on the basis of mechanistic and mechanism non-invoking equations. The mechanism-based study was made by choosing different functional forms of α (fractional decomposition), assumed to be governing the rate controlling processes and fitting them into MacCallum-Tanner equation⁷. The mechanism-non-invoking treatment was based on the Coats-Redfern equation⁸.

Experimental

Potassium chlorate ('Baker Analysed' Reagent grade) and potassium bromate (M & B grade) were dried at 120° for several hours and kept in desiccator before use. The metal oxides, viz., CuO and MnO₂ used were of BDH grade, and had purity above 98%. The oxides were ignited at 500° and kept in desiccator before use. The metal oxides and oxysalts were of mesh size 200-240. In all experiments 0.2 g sample of the salts was mixed intimately with 50 mg of the oxide before taking TG traces.

The TG traces were taken in a Stanton recording thermobalance (model TR-1). Heating rate was 4° min⁻¹ and the atmosphere was static air. The amount of KBr and KCl left behind in all the experiments agreed well with the calculated values and the instrument reading.

Results and Discussion

The total weight loss in all cases were 78 ± 1 mg for KClO₃ and 58 ± 1 mg for KBrO₃. For purpose

of brevity, the TG traces, redrawn as mass versus temperature, and the DTG curves are not shown. Excepting the catalysed decomposition of KClO₃ by CuO, the other catalysed processes proceeded to completion immediately after reaching the peak temperature of decomposition (T_s). In such cases the α values were taken only upto the peak temperature of decomposition. The temperature range of decomposition of potassium chlorate mixed with CuO had a greater spread (T_r - T_i = 140°), whereas that for the other catalysed decompositions was considerably less as revealed by Table 1; T_r and T_i being the temperatures of completion and initiation respectively of the process. An increase in the temperature span for the decomposition of the system, KClO₃-CuO has been reported previously also⁹. The effects of the metal oxides were not then explained on the basis of change in E*, ΔS^* etc. (where E* and ΔS^* are energy and entropy of activation), but explanations were based on the catalysts' influence on melting of the substrate and their semiconductive properties. It could be that the phenomenon be specific in nature with respect to the catalyst substrate system. The more ordered configuration of the transition state, when CuO is present (as shown by the change in ΔS^*), and the large decrease in E* while the mechanistic mode remained unchanged can result in a slower enhancement of rate with increase in temperature. (In the case of KBrO₃ there is change in the mechanism itself compared to the uncatalysed decomposition, when it occurs in presence of CuO). In all the cases where metal oxides were used the T_r, T_s and T_i values were lowered substantially.

The TG data of all the decompositions fitted well into the Coats-Redfern equation for first order process. The Coats-Redfern plots, and the plots based on mechanistic equations, excepting the mechanistic plots for the decomposition of KBrO₃, are not given. The frequency factors, energies and

System	TABLE 1			Temperature range of decomposition
	T ₁ K	T ₂ K	T ₁ K	
KClO ₃	773	868	893	120°
KBrO ₃	643	693	723	80.
KClO ₃ + CuO(25% w/w)	573	663	713	140
KBrO ₃ + CuO(25% w/w)	583	645	648	65
KClO ₃ + MnO ₂ (25% w/w)	553	603	613	60
KBrO ₃ + MnO ₂ (25% w/w)	573	625	633	60

entropies of activation etc. for the decomposition of KClO₃ and mixtures of KClO₃ with CuO and with MnO₂ were calculated using the Coats-Redfern equation and mechanism based equations. These are given in Table 2. The corresponding values for the potassium bromate decomposition based on Coats-Redfern equation were taken from elsewhere⁸ and those based on mechanistic equations were calculated.

Generally the mechanism based study has been applied to isothermal weight change processes only. However, recently there have been extensions of this approach to dynamic thermogravimetric studies also⁹. The fractional decomposition, α , and the rate of solid state decomposition reaction are related by the general equation, $\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k.f(\alpha)$, where $f(\alpha)$ is a function of α given by the rate controlling process and $k = Ze^{-E^*/RT}$, (Z being frequency factor and E*, activation energy). The integral,

$$\int_0^\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)} = g(\alpha), \text{ and}$$

$g(\alpha)$ can have different forms for different mechanistic models⁹. In the present study six different model forms of $g(\alpha)$ have been employed viz.,

$$\alpha^2, [1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3}]^2, [-\ln(1 - \alpha)],$$

$$[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{1/2}, [-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{1/3} \text{ and } 1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3}.$$

Plots of $\log g(\alpha)$ values vs $\frac{1}{T}$ is linear only for the $\log g(\alpha)$ that corresponds to the probable rate controlling process⁹. When more than one such linear plots are obtainable for different forms of $g(\alpha)$ plotted against $\frac{1}{T}$, the probable operating mechanism can be selected by comparing the values of E*, Z etc. from such plots with those obtainable from mechanism non-invoking general kinetic study.

In the present study we used the MacCallum-Tanner equation of the form :

$$\log g(\alpha) = \log \frac{ZE^*}{\phi R} - 0.48E^* \times 10^4$$

$$- \left(\frac{0.449 + 0.217E^*}{T} \right) \times 10^3$$

(where ϕ is heating rate) for evaluating E* and Z from such linear plots. Representative plots showing the influence of the function $g(\alpha)$ on the plot of $\log g(\alpha)$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$ is given in Fig. 1. In cases where

more than one such linear plots were obtained, the probable operating mechanism was selected by comparing the values of E* and Z obtained from $\log g(\alpha)$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$ plots with those obtained from the

Coats-Redfern equation. It may be pointed out here that in this case the $g(\alpha)$ employed in the Coats-Redfern equation has the form, $\ln w_\alpha/w_\infty - w$ (where w_α is mass loss at completion of the reaction and w is mass loss at temperature T), which is equivalent to $[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]$. The values of E*, Z and ΔS^* and the probable operating mechanism are given in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Mechanistic plots: $-\log g(\alpha)$ versus $\frac{10^3}{T}$ for the decomposition of KBrO₃.

It is interesting to note that the CuO catalysed decomposition of KClO₃ and KBrO₃ have similar mode of decomposition, in view of the similarities in the activation parameters and frequency factor. In either case there is marked decrease in activation

TABLE 2

System	Coats-Redfern equation			Mechanistic equation		
	E* K.J mole ⁻¹	Z, sec ⁻¹	ΔS* J mole ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	E* K.J mole ⁻¹	Z, sec ⁻¹	Equation applicable
KClO ₃	363.1	2.45 × 10 ²¹	155.8	317.3	2 × 10 ¹⁸	Avrami
KBrO ₃	433.0	9.4 × 10 ²⁹	310.3	469.0	1.8 × 10 ²⁵	Mampel
KClO ₃ + CuO(25% w/w)	177.4	3.55 × 10 ¹¹	-35.0	168.5	2.48 × 10 ¹⁸	Avrami
KBrO ₃ + CuO(25% w/w)	168.0	3.8 × 10 ¹⁰	-48.8	157.0	7.3 × 10 ¹⁰	Avrami
KClO ₃ + MnO ₂ (25% w/w)	420.1	1.21 × 10 ²⁶	325.1	418.6	8.7 × 10 ²⁷	Mampel
KBrO ₃ + MnO ₂ (25% w/w)	186.0	7.94 × 10 ¹²	-4.1	164.9	1.86 × 10 ¹²	Avrami

energy and the entropy of activation becomes considerably less, and have comparable values (Table 2). The decrease in activation entropy suggests the possibility of formation of chemisorbed transition state, the catalysis being due to lowering of activation energy. The mechanism found probable for both the cases are the Avrami¹⁰ model equation, viz, $1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3}$ for $g(\alpha)$. The probable rate controlling process would be phase boundary reaction assuming spherical symmetry. This is so in the decomposition of KBrO₃ mixed with MnO₂ also. However, the decomposition of KClO₃ in the presence of MnO₂ showed interesting departure from this trend. The acceleration in rate seems to be purely an entropy effect as there is more than a two fold increase in ΔS^* compared to the uncatalysed decomposition, in spite of marginal increase in activation energy. A similar behaviour was reported⁶ for the thermal decomposition of potassium bromate mixed with TiO₂. It appears therefore that MnO₂ catalyses the decomposition by increasing the disorder of the transition state considerably. The mode of this decomposition according to mechanistic treatment was found to follow the Mampel¹¹ equation i.e., $-\ln(1 - \alpha)$ for $g(\alpha)$. The reaction proceeds by a random nucleation process, that is, with formation of a nucleus on every particle. The normal decomposition of KClO₃ was found to follow the Avrami model equation with phase boundary reaction and that of

KBrO₃ to follow the Mampel model equation assuming random nucleation.

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